

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D4.3 - Elaboration of training materials

Authors:

Esti SANVICENTE (3OC), Tomáš PERUTKA (EAZK), Xavier PALOMÉ (DDGI),
Georgia PILIGOTSI (RDFC)

May 2024 (M34) - WP4, D4.3

Technical References

Project Acronym	ePLANET
Project Title	European Local Public Authorities' Network for driving the Energy Transition

Deliverable No. & Title	D4.3 - Elaboration of training materials
Type of deliverable	R (document, report);
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP4 - User Empowerment
Lead beneficiary	10 (3OC)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	4 (FEDARENE), 6 (DDGI), 7 (RDFC), 8 (EAZK) 9 (LIMA), CIMNE
Due date of deliverable	31 May 2024
Actual submission date	31 May 2024

Authors	Esti SANVICENTE (3OC), Tomáš PERUTKA (EAZK), Xavier PALOMÉ (DDGI), Georgia PILIGOTSI (RDFC)
Contributors	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE), Eleni CHATZIGEORGIU and Katerina SFAKIANAKI' (CRES), Josep Maria GRANOLLERS and Marta CHAFER (ICAEN), Segis VERDAGUER (LIMA), Ola BARRACHINA (LIMA)

Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
01	30 January 2024	First draft of D4.1	Esti SANVICENTE (3OC)
02	30 April 2024	Update of activities	Esti SANVICENTE (3OC) and responsible partners
03	May 2024	Review of activities with responsible partners	All
04	31 May 2024	Final draft	Esti SANVICENTE (3OC)
05	31 May 2024	Peer-review	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)

Content

1	Introduction	9
1.1	Organisation of the report	9
2	ePLANET CBP structure	10
2.1	Beneficiaries of the capacity building activities	10
2.1.1	<i>Profiles of participants in private activities</i>	10
2.1.2	<i>Profiles of participants in public activities</i>	10
2.2	Thematic areas	10
2.3	Learning outcomes and objectives	12
2.4	Activity format	13
3	Reporting on pilot specific capacity building activities.....	14
Pilot 1. CRETE ISLAND - Overview of the CBP	14	
3.1.1	<i>Detailed reporting of the capacity building activities in Crete.....</i>	16
Pilot 2. GIRONA PROVINCE - Overview of the CBP.....	34	
3.1.2	<i>Detailed reporting of the capacity building activities in Girona</i>	36
Pilot 3. ZLÍN REGION - Overview of the CBP	54	
3.1.3	<i>Detailed reporting of the capacity building activities in Zlín region</i>	56
4	Key takeaways and next steps	72

Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofunded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

The development of ePLANET is justified to deploy Energy Transition (ET) in the public sector, for which the following challenges are targeted:

- Improving coordination between local authorities and regional governments
- Enhancing the decision-making process in the deployment of ET projects
- Providing coherence and consistency to the energy transition measures (ETM) to be implemented
- Encouraging the digitalisation of measures and plans
- Enabling an interoperable ecosystem of data and tools
- **Building capacity of local authorities**

All these targeted objectives will give the needed support for the energy transition decision-making process and its practical implementation.

The present report is part of WP4, User empowerment. WP4 aims to empower policymakers, public officers, new ePLANET governance figures and key stakeholders with the necessary tools to implement Energy Transition Measures (ETM) with enough information and the proper tools.

In Task 4.1, we investigated the main barriers and capacity building needs that ePLANET local authorities face when developing energy transition planning and implementation. In Task 4.2, we co-designed the capacity-building strategy and program for each ePLANET pilot territory. The present deliverable offers a comprehensive report on the capacity-building activities implemented in each pilot territory, outlining the engagement strategy and providing a detailed description of each activity. Finally, the last section summarises the key takeaways from the capacity-building program and outlines the next steps.

Here is an overview of the capacity building program implemented in each pilot territory:
Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Crete Island:

Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Girona Province:

Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Zlín Region:

List of Tables

Table 3-1 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Crete Island and Greece ... 15
Table 3-2 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Girona Province..... 35
Table 3-3 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Zlín Region..... 55

List of Figures

Figure 2-1 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme..... 10

Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CBP	Capacity Building Programme
EAZK	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESCO	Energy Service Company
ETM	Energy Transition Measures
EU	European
DDGI	Girona Provincial Council
OTE	Energy Transition Offices
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan

1 Introduction

The ePLANET project is divided into 7 work packages working on governance, digitalisation, capacity building, replication and networking, communication, and dissemination.

The present report is part of WP4, User empowerment. WP4 aims to empower policymakers, public officers, new ePLANET governance figures and key stakeholders with the necessary tools to implement Energy Transition Measures (ETM) with enough information and the proper tools.

In Task 4.1, we investigated the main barriers and capacity building needs that ePLANET local authorities face when developing energy transition planning and implementation. The outcomes of this first task, together with the previous ePLANET outputs in WP2, were taken as a point of departure for a package of work, which involved the co-development of tailor-made training materials on ETM addressing the main requirements and needs of the different target groups.

In Task 4.2, we co-designed the capacity-building strategy and program for each ePLANET pilot territory. The present deliverable, D4.3, reports on the 24 capacity-building activities implemented over a 12- to 14-month period in 2023-2024.

1.1 Organisation of the report

This report is organised as follows: Section 2 details how we have organised and structured the ePLANET Capacity Building Programme (CBP), covering the participant profile, target numbers, selected thematic areas, and main learning objectives. Section 3, the core of D4.3, offers a comprehensive report on the capacity-building activities implemented in each pilot territory, outlining the engagement strategy and providing a detailed description of each activity. Finally, the last section summarises the key takeaways from the capacity-building program and outlines the next steps.

2 ePLANET CBP structure

Figure 2-1 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme

2.1 Beneficiaries of the capacity building activities

The beneficiaries of ePLANET capacity building activities were the project's main stakeholders, including:

- Local authorities
- Regional authorities
- Energy agencies
- Energy Transition facilitators (Urban planners, sustainability and Energy experts, ESCOs, investors and industry stakeholders).

These beneficiaries were invited to participate in various capacity-building activities based on whether they were private or public, as well as the specific theme and objective.

2.1.1 Profiles of participants in private activities

By participant in private activities, we mean a representative of a local authority in the pilot territory, which can be a city, a municipality, or an energy transition facilitator working for the local authority.

2.1.2 Profiles of participants in public activities

On the other hand, by participant in public activities, ePLANET refers to all stakeholders, including local authorities, regional energy and climate agencies, all energy transition facilitators, students, and citizens as a whole.

2.2 Thematic areas

According to the capacity building needs assessment and discussion with partners, the capacity building activities were grouped into **five thematic areas**:

| BUILDINGS

Municipal Buildings: Covered buildings and facilities owned, managed, or controlled by public authorities. Facilities referred to energy consuming entities that are not buildings, such as wastewater treatment plants.

Private Buildings: Covered buildings owned, managed, or controlled by private individuals or businesses. These referred primarily to the tertiary sector (services), such as private companies, banks, commercial, and retail activities, hospitals, etc. and residential buildings, including social housing. According to the EU project [PROSPECT+](#), local and regional authorities perceive this area as important but difficult and have not much experience.

| TRANSPORT

Covered the provision of and management of inter provincial mass transit systems by public authorities, as well as shared mobility services and other type of private transport.

| PUBLIC LIGHTING

Covered the provision of public lighting (e.g. street lighting and traffic lights) owned or operated by public authorities. Non-municipal public lighting is under private buildings. According to the EU project [PROSPECT+](#), although this area is perceived as manageable by local and regional authorities, there are many questions and doubts related to the choice of technologies and the implementation and management of projects.

| Renewable Energy Sources (RES)

Covered all those interventions falling under the thematic area of RES; climate change adaptation; local electricity production e.g., wind power, hydroelectric power, photovoltaic; and local heat/cold production e.g., combined heat and power and district heating plant.

| CROSS SECTORAL FINANCE

The need for specific support in finance was a matter of consensus for a large majority of municipalities in ePLANET pilot territories. Innovative financing instruments were highlighted, indicating strong needs and interest among municipalities. Therefore, the cross-sectoral finance area primarily focused on these types of financing schemes:

Innovative Financing Schemes: By innovative financing schemes, ePLANET referred to non-traditional ways of raising funds and facilitating sustainable energy and climate investments by mixing different sources (own fund, public and private funds) or engaging different partners (e.g. citizens, private sector) outside of established financial institutions (e.g. banks).

The innovative financing instruments that ePLANET focused on are aligned with those of the EU project [PROSPECT+](#):

- Citizen finance (crowdfunding and cooperatives).
- Energy Performance Contracting (EPC).
- Internal contracting (intracontracting).
- Green Bonds: Local government (or their agencies) can issue green bonds to fund their sustainable energy and climate actions.

- Guarantee funds (loan guarantees provided to lenders which serve as buffers against first losses of non-payment by the borrowers).
- Soft loans (loans below market rates and with longer payback periods derived from public funding to facilitate investments).
- Revolving funds established to finance a continuing cycle of investments through initial amounts received from its shareholders.
- Third-party financing (debt financing where project financing comes from a third party), e.g. ESCO which is not user or customer.

2.3 Learning outcomes and objectives

In the context of ePLANET, learning objectives are defined as sharing of knowledge, skills, and competencies. The following is a range of learning objectives that were achieved by participants - in part or as a whole - in the ePLANET CBP, depending on their needs studied. The detailed learning objectives per activity are presented in Section 3.

- Understand the ePLANET platform and the different modules that integrate it (UC1, UC2, UC3, and UC4).
- Apply tools to
 - Classify and determine the energy consumption trends of your municipality (and CO2 emissions).
 - Discuss and benchmark the different actions defined by the SECAPs.
- Apply ePLANET UC2 to
 - Understand building consumption data (i.e. historical energy consumption of each building, aggregated energy consumption by energy source and month, evolution of global energy consumption...).
 - Visualise the energy performance of their buildings and other relevant KPIs such as energy usage intensity.
 - Benchmark and compare the energy performance of a particular building with one of other similar buildings.
- Apply ePLANET UC3 and UC4 tools to
 - Visualise renewable energy generation at a municipal level.
 - Compare the renewable energy generation between different municipalities.
 - Visualise the PV energy generation estimation on each rooftop and compare between municipalities.
 - Learn how to set a possible energy community and visualise its users' estimated self-sufficient rates.
- Understand what Governance, analyse the current status of the governance in the different pilot territories and learn from experiences on other regions.
- Understand the innovative financing schemes that are relevant under the selected thematic areas, examine selected case studies on these sectors (with a focus on small municipalities) and reflect on how barriers and challenges were overcome.
- Understand the causes, mechanisms and consequences of Climate Change in different sectors and identify actions to reduce our individual and collective carbon footprint.

2.4 Activity format

The ePLANET CBP included three types of activity formats, based on the survey needs assessment carried out:

Online sessions: ePLANET organised online sessions in the form of webinars, facilitated by ePLANET partners and featuring external experts on the respective topics. The GoToMeeting platform was utilised for these sessions, and participants received a link in advance from the designated ePLANET partner to join the online sessions.

In person activities: In-person meetings can take the form of training sessions or workshops and were characterised as activities during which the facilitator visits the pilot territory to enhance knowledge exchange and capacity building. An in-person activity typically lasts between half a day and a maximum of one day, depending on whether several activities are organised on the same day.

Site Visits: implemented in WP5.

3 Reporting on pilot specific capacity building activities

Pilot 1. CRETE ISLAND - Overview of the CBP

The capacity building program for Crete consisted of eight types of activities, incorporating one informative session, five technical training sessions on the ePLANET platform, three content-focused sessions, one webinar on innovative financing, and two awareness-raising sessions on Climate Change to engage a diverse audience. A total 11 sessions were organised in the Greek language.

 350 participants participated - territory and scale up

Table 3-1 below shows the list of the different activities and the dates.

Timeline: ePLANET officially launched the Capacity Building Programme in Crete in June 2023, following an informative webinar organised in February 2023. The duration was around 14 months, with adjustments made to certain activities based on participant availability and the work and time plans of the municipalities.

Engagement strategy: The main objective of the capacity building activities organised from WP4 was to attract municipalities and other key stakeholders in Crete. However, two activities, namely, 7 and 8, were co-organised with Work Package 5 (WP5) and involved stakeholders at the national level.

How?

- **Informative webinar:** A general introduction to the ePLANET project, tools, and the Capacity Building Programme. One such webinar was organised at the beginning of the CBP, and guidance materials were made available for participants through the ePLANET website. This allowed them to better understand the CBP structure, how to participate, as well as the themes covered and indicative **dates**.
- **For private activities:** Communication primarily consisted of phone calls and mailing, with tailored invitations for each activity.
- **For public activities:** Mailing was utilised in specific instances, along with the use of online channels such as LinkedIn and websites belonging to responsible partners.
- **RDFC and CRES contribution:** RDFC contributed to the invitation list and promoted the events at territory level. CRES, on the other hand, contributed to attract participants at national level. Both participated in the facilitation of the sessions.

Table 3-1 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Crete Island and Greece

3.1.1 Detailed reporting of the capacity building activities in Crete

ACTIVITY #1 Presentation of ePLANET project, pilot activities and CBP in Crete	
Type of activity:	Webinar - Private activity
Date & location:	01/02/2023 @online
General info & needs addressed:	The Kick-off webinar aimed to inform municipalities in Crete about the ePLANET project and its tools. It also served as an introduction to the MoAs and the Capacity Building Program. Initial feedback on the CBP, including content and indicative dates, was collected during the meeting.
Responsible partner/facilitators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - contributed to the promotion and engagement of participants and co-organised the session. • CRES - acted as the main point of contact for all participants, offering information about the full scope of ePLANET. It also led the co-organisation of the webinar and presented the CBP and the various activities in the local language.
Target audience:	In this first informative webinar, the 18 representatives from Municipalities of Crete (who have SECAPs) participated. The recording of the webinar contributed to maximise the visibility to other municipalities.
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about the ePLANET project, its tools, and the opportunities it creates. • Learn about the three pilots in ePLANET, with a special focus on the pilot in Crete. • Learn about the MoA for the testing phase. • Get an overview of the CBP for Crete. • Gain a better understanding of the CBP structure, participation modalities, and the thematic areas covered in the learning cycle.
Agenda:	1h duration addressing ePLANET presentation, introduction to the pilots, benefits arising from the participation of municipalities in the e-PLANET project and the signing of the Cooperation Agreement
Links to presentation:	To be uploaded.
Link to the recording:	The event was not recorded.

ACTIVITY #1 Presentation of ePLANET project, pilot activities and CBP in Crete @online

Οφέλη που προκύπτουν από την συμμετοχή των Δήμων στο έργο e-PLANET και την υπογραφή του Συμφώνου Συνεργασίας:

Με τη συμμετοχή στο Πρόγραμμα και την υπογραφή του Συμφώνου Συνεργασίας με το έργο e-PLANET, οι Δήμοι της Κρήτης θα έχουν τη δυνατότητα να:

- **Οπτικοποιήσουν και να κατανοήσουν άμεσα τα ενεργειακά δεδομένα και στοιχεία που διαθέτουν**
- Βρουν τρόπους για να επισυνάψουν την επίτευξη στόμων που έχουν θέσει στα Σχέδια Ενεργειακής Μετάβασης ή/και τα Σχέδια Δράσης Αειφόρου Ενέργειας και Κλιματικής Αλλαγής
- **Προβλέψουν τα Σχέδια Ενεργειακής Μετάβασης ή/και τα Σχέδια Δράσης Αειφόρου Ενέργειας και Κλιματικής Αλλαγής στο ευρύ κοινό και τα επιτυχημένα αποτελέσματα**
- Εργάζονται όσο γίνεται περισσότερες ομάδες δράσης και **τοπικούς φορείς** στην υλοποίησή τους
- Συμμετέχουν σε **προγράμματα εκπαίδευσης και ανάπτυξης δεξιοτήτων** (capacity building) που θα απευθύνονται τόσο σε στελέχη των Τεχνικών Υπηρεσιών όσο και των αρχών

Ειδικότερα, συνεργαζόμενοι για τη διαχείριση των ενεργειακών τους δεδομένων οι Δήμοι της Κρήτης μπορούν να:

- Διαχειριστούν αποτελεσματικότερα τα ενεργειακά τους δεδομένα και τα Σχέδια Ενεργειακής Μετάβασης ή Σχέδια Δράσης Αειφόρου Ενέργειας και Κλιματικής Αλλαγής, καθώς μέσω της άμεσης παραφόρας του έργου θα είναι δυνατός ο άμεσος ανταγωνισμός και η **κρίσιμη αποκάλυψη** τους επιτείνοντας έτσι την καλύτερη ανάλυσή.
- **Ανταλλάσσουν πληροφορίες, χρήσιμα εργαλεία και καλές πρακτικές** με άλλους τους άλλους δήμους μέσω μιας σύγχρονης ψηφιακής πλατφόρμας μέσω γραφημάτων και χερσών.
- Εφορμάσουν μέτρα και δράσεις ενεργειακής απόδοσης **συνεργατικά** με άλλους Δήμους επιτυγχάνοντας αποτελεσματικότερη χρήση των πόρων τους.
- **Αξιοποιήσουν βελτισμένα συστήματα παρακολούθησης** της αποτελεσματικότητας και των μέτρων και δράσεων που υλοποιούνται.

EUROPEAN PUBLIC LOCAL AUTHORITIES' NETWORK FOR DRIVING THE ENERGY TRANSITION

Ευρωπαϊκό έργο ePLANET - Στόχοι και κύριες δράσεις

KAPE | **CRES** | CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING

Κατερίνα Στρακανονάκη, Φυσικός Κτηρίων, MSc
Ελένη Χατζηγεωργίου, Πολιτικός Μηχανικός ΕΜΠ, MSc

Διαδικτυακό εργαστήριο (Webinar)
01 Φεβρουαρίου 2023

UC2: ANALYSIS OF THE ENERGY PERFORMANCE OF THE PUBLIC BUILDING STOCK

Κάθε κτήριο αναλύεται χωριστά σε ένα νέο υπολογιστικό φύλλο στο οποίο μπορούμε να δούμε τα χαρακτηριστικά του κτηρίου καθώς και όλα τα δεδομένα της κατανάλωσης ενέργειας ανά μήνα.

ACTIVITY #2 Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1	
Type of activity:	In person workshop - Private activity
Date & location:	Workshop organised in different sessions: 08-09/06/2023 and 21/06/2023@Chania (Crete)
General info & needs addressed:	Use Case 1-Digitalisation of SECAP will include several dashboards to show the mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. It will also enable a comparative visualisation of the SECAPs of the municipalities belonging to Crete Island.
Responsible partner/facilitators:	Regional Development Fund of Crete for the organisation of the whole event and CIMNE and CRES for their active involvement in the workshop. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - organised the event, taking charge of promotional activities and participant engagement. • CRES - collaborated as a co-facilitator for the in-person workshop and translated support materials into Greek. • CIMNE - produced guidance materials in English for participants and conducted training sessions to familiarise participants with the platform.
Target participants:	19 participants, representing six municipalities in Crete: Chania, Platania, Kantanou-Selinou, Minoa Pediadas, Viannos and Arhanes-Asterousia.
Learning objectives:	Gain proficiency in utilising the various tools developed by the project to enhance the management and governance of Energy Transition initiatives. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehend the functionality of the ePLANET platform and the UC1 tool. • Acquire practical skills in utilising ePLANET by: • Applying UC1 tools to categorise and analyse energy consumption trends in your municipality (including CO2 emissions). • Engaging in discussions and benchmarking activities related to the various actions outlined in SECAPs.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of ePLANET project, ePLANET platform and UC1. • Exercises on UC1 use cases and Q&A
Links to presentation:	All manuals will be uploaded.
Link to the recording:	The event was not recorded.

ACTIVITY #2 Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 - 08 June 2023 @Chania

ACTIVITY #2b Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 - 21 June 2023 @Heraklion, Crete

ACTIVITY #3 Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1/UC2/UC3	
Type of activity:	Hybrid workshop - Private activity
Date & location:	Workshop organised in different sessions: 10-11-12/07/2023 @RDFC premises in Heraklion (Crete) 3 extra workshops following the launching of the testing of ePLANET platform. Most of the workshops were hybrid, with CIMNE and CRES providing extra guidance and clarification online.
General info & needs addressed:	<p>Use Case 1-Digitalisation of SECAP includes several dashboards to show the mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. It will also enable a comparative visualisation of the SECAPs of the municipalities belonging to Crete Island.</p> <p>Use Case 2- Analysis of the energy performance of public buildings includes several dashboards to show historic benchmarking of the building, comparative benchmarking and specific KPIs. It also consists of a “landscape unit” observatory and the citizen portal, which both allow general citizens to be aware of the energy consumption of the public sector at municipal level.</p> <p>Use case 3- Geo tools for the promotion of energy communities</p>
Responsible partner/facilitators:	<p>Regional Development Fund of Crete for the organisation of the whole event and CIMNE and CRES for their active involvement in the workshop.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - organised the event, taking charge of promotional activities and participant engagement. • CRES - collaborated as a co-facilitator for the in-person workshop and translated support materials into Greek. • CIMNE - produced guidance materials in English for participants and conducted training sessions to familiarise participants with the platform.
Target participants:	8 participants, representing two municipalities in Crete: Herakleion and Hersonissos
Learning objectives:	<p>Gain proficiency in utilising the various tools developed by the project to enhance the management and governance of Energy Transition initiatives.</p> <p>Each day was devoted to a different municipality. The 1st day, the workshop was held at Ierapetra municipality, including a discussion with the municipal energy teams. 2nd day at Rethymno municipality and 3rd day at the municipality of Agios Nikolaos.</p>
Agenda:	Presentation of different UCs of ePLANET, showcase and Q&A session
Links to presentation:	All technical manuals will be uploaded.
Link to the recording:	The event was not recorded.

ACTIVITY #3 Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1/UC2- 10-11-12 July 2023 @ Ierapetra

ACTIVITY #4a The Climate Sprint	
Type of activity:	In person workshop - Public
Date & location:	27 September 2023 @Hellenic Mediterranean University, Heraklion, Crete
General info & needs addressed:	Climate Change is a complex problem that impacts us all. However, as revealed in the analysis of Task 4.1, it is poorly understood in the three pilot areas and among the general population. The Climate Sprint has prompted stakeholders in this pilot to gain a better understanding of climate change's consequences and take constructive action.
Responsible partner/facilitators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3OC - facilitated the activity as an accredited facilitator of Climate Fresk and experts in climate transformation • CRES - supported the activity by co-facilitating in the local language and assisting with the organisation. • RDFC - contributed to the promotion and engagement of participants
Target audience:	15 participants - We engaged with two groups of postgraduate students, all with backgrounds in electrical engineering.
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaining a better understanding of climate change and its consequences in different sectors. • Clarify technical questions with scientific base (based on IPCC reports) • Learning about orders of magnitude in CO2 emissions. • Getting familiar with Carbon Footprint and how it is measured. • Identifying impactful actions to reduce individual emissions.
Agenda:	<p>10h - 10:15: Introduction to ePLANET project and its role in the climate transformation</p> <p>10h15 - 11h30: Building the Climate Fresk 🌍</p> <p>11h30 - 12:30: What is my footprint? 🧠 Individual actions to reduce it 🦋</p>
Links to presentation:	Link to Climate Fresk cards in Greek: https://climatefresk.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/The-Climate-Fresk-EL-GR-Adults-V8.1.pdf
Link to the recording:	The event was not recorded

ACTIVITY #4a The Climate Sprint - 27 September 2023 @Hellenic Mediterranean University

Δεν μπορούμε να φτιάξουμε ό,τι δεν μπορούμε να κατανοήσουμε και να μετρήσουμε!

ACTIVITY #4b Additional Climate Fresks	
Type of activity:	In person workshops - Public
Date & location:	29/2/2024 and 6/3/2024 @ Rethymnon Crete, Second chance school for adults
General info & needs addressed:	After the training session organised by 3OC for the RDFC team on "Climate Fresk," a French educational tool designed to understand the causes and consequences of climate change, the RDFC team organised two sessions for the general public.
Responsible partner/facilitators:	The first session was facilitated by Mrs Georgia Piligotsi, member of the RDFC Team for e-PLANET project, actively involved in the 1st Climate Fresk workshop that took place in Crete Sept2023. The second session was supported by Mrs Lina Avramidou, an English teacher at the school, who helped the students learn the English version of each key term.
Target audience:	A total of 20 people were split into 2 groups of 10 people each. The target group for these two events consisted of adults and students of the Second Chance School of Rethymnon aged 20 to 70 years old.
Learning objectives:	The workshop lasted 3 hours and the participants were actively engaged to recognise the interlinkages of all the different dimensions and sectors associated with the problem of climate change by identifying the cause and effect of each human activity. The structure of the workshop gave them the chance to cooperate and work in teams so as to set the cards in order thus understand the way intense energy consumption leads to climate change. At the end of the 2 sessions, students were able to correctly answer the following questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the responsibility of human activities on climate change? • How would you feel if you were invited to host some climate refugees who arrived in our country due to the adverse impact of climate change in their home countries? • How does war affect climate change? • Do you believe it is possible to mitigate climate change in any way?
Agenda:	On Wednesday, February 29th, the attendees of the first cycle of studies were introduced to the multidimensional concept of climate change and the training tool named "Climate Fresk," which was developed based on the 4th and 5th IPCC Reports, translated into Greek, and delivered to the project team of RDFC. Following this first round, the workshop was repeated on Wednesday, March 6th, with the attendees of the second cycle of studies at the school.
Link to the recording:	The event was not recorded

ACTIVITY #5 Conference session on the Governance of Energy Transition

Type of activity:	Hybrid event in the form of workshop
Date & location:	18 October 2023 @Heraklion Crete, Capsis Hotel
General info & needs addressed:	One of the objectives of the ePLANET project is to reframe the current governance model and design and establish a new clustering governance model to facilitate the deployment of energy transition projects in each pilot territory, creating and improving coordination between different municipalities acting together. As an integral component of the training Seminar/Webinar & National Conference dedicated to Municipalities on Energy Transition, the specific aim of this session was to spotlight exemplary practices in energy transition governance, particularly within the realm of public bodies.
Responsible partner/facilitators:	RDFC - Dr. Nikolaos Zografakis,
Target audience:	30 physically present / ~ 100 online The conference aimed to engage individuals and entities with an interest in the field of energy transition, including municipalities, businesses, social organisations, and citizens. Attendees comprised representatives from both public and private sectors, as well as project managers and technicians from Greece and Cyprus, among others.
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what Governance is at practical level (how it is being deployed to facilitate energy transition projects) • Analyse the current status of the governance in Crete Island • Co-design the different governance methodologies to simplify policy-making in Crete Island Learn from other ePLANET pilot regions.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ePLANET Governance Model • Showcasing Good Practices in Energy Transition Governance through Public Bodies • Highlighting Projects in Various Sectors
Link to the recording:	Event not recorded for GDPR reasons

ACTIVITY #6 Conference session to showcase of tools and initiatives for the promotion of energy communities

Type of activity:	Hybrid event in the form of workshop
Date & location:	19 October 2023 @Heraklion Crete, Capsis Hotel
General info & needs addressed:	As an integral component of the training Seminar/Webinar & National Conference dedicated to Municipalities on Energy Transition, the specific aim of this session was to showcase the advances and the progress made so far from the successful example of the Minoa Energy Community (EC). The biggest EC in Greece. The different sectors and projects where the EC can be actively involved were presented, including social cohesion and energy poverty, as well as electromobility and use of RES for the energy-water nexus in Crete.
Responsible partner/facilitators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC • Mrs Ermioni Giality (Region of Crete) • Mr George Viskadouros (Minoan EC) • Mr Antonis Kozyrakis (Minoan EC)
Target audience:	30 physically present / ~ 100 online
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquire knowledge of best practices observed in existing energy communities within Crete and nationally. • Understand the functionality of the ePLANET UC3 module Geo tools, specifically designed for promoting energy communities and assessing their potential
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crete and Energy Transition: tools and projects • MINOA Energy Community: Activities and projects • Geotherchnical Information Infrastructure GIS CRETE - the new technologies and tools and their contribution to Cretan Municipalities
Links to presentation:	All presentation will be included in the repository by the end of the project.
Link to the recording:	Event not recorded for GDPR reasons

ACTIVITIES #5 & #6 - 18-19 October 2023 @ Hotel Capsis Astoria Heraklion Hotel, Heraklion

ACTIVITY #7 Innovative financing - Focus on Energy Efficiency and buildings

Type of activity:	Webinar
Date & location:	07 February 2024 @TEAMS
General info & needs addressed:	This webinar addressed one of the capacity-building needs identified in Task 4.1, which is financing mechanisms for energy efficiency projects. It mainly addressed to representatives of Regions, Municipalities and other public bodies involved in the planning, implementation and financing of energy transition plans and energy saving projects for public buildings.
Responsible facilitators:	CRES and Three o'clock and in collaboration with PROSPECT+ project
Target audience:	38 participants from municipalities, regional authorities, universities, companies and eu organisations.
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The learning objectives of the course included gaining an understanding of various financing mechanisms for energy efficiency projects, such as Energy Performance Contracts and EU best practices demonstrated by projects like REFINE. Participants explored case studies from the EU-funded projects PRODESA and SMAFIN/SMAFIN Expanded to grasp the outcomes and prospects of energy-saving initiatives in buildings, particularly focusing on municipal structures. Additionally, the course aimed to equip learners with insights into capacity-building programs like PROSPECT+ designed to empower public authorities in financing sustainable energy plans. Through these topics, participants developed the knowledge to navigate and contribute to the field of energy efficiency financing effectively.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to ePLANET - Katerina Sfakianaki, Building Physicist MSc, CRES Financing energy efficiency projects through Energy Performance Contracts, EU best practices - the REFINE project - Aristotelis Botzios-Valaskakis, Mechanical Engineer MSc, Division of Development Programs, CRES Financing energy saving projects in buildings. Outcomes and prospects - The SMAFIN & SMAFIN Expanded projects - Kiki Papadopoulou, Head of Dissemination of RES & EE Applications Department, SMAFIN & SMAFIN Expanded Coordinator, CRES Energy renovation of Municipal buildings in Vari, Voula, Vouliagmeni through Energy Performance Contracting - The PRODESA project - Argyro Giakoumi, Physicist MSc, Energy Policy Analysis Department, CRES How PROSPECT+ builds the capacity of public authorities in financing their sustainable energy plans Discussion - Sophia Theodoropoulou, TEESlab, University of Piraeus
Link to the recording:	Event recorded link

ACTIVITY #7 Innovative financing - Focus on Energy Efficiency and buildings - 07/02/2024 @ONLINE

SMAFIN
Smart Financing Implementation

Χρηματοδότηση έργων εξοικονόμησης ενέργειας στα κτήρια – Τα έργα SMAFIN και SMAFIN Expanded
E-Planet, 7 Φεβρουαρίου 2024

Καθ. Παπαδοπούλου, ΚΑΤΙΕ
Συντονίστρια SMAFIN & SMAFIN Expanded

Κύριος στόχος

Ανάπτυξη και εφαρμογή μιας μεθοδολογίας για την ενίσχυση της πολυεπίπεδης διακυβέρνησης των δημόσιων αρχών και τη συντονισμένη υιοθέτηση μέτρων στην κατεύθυνση της ενεργειακής μετάβασης, με στόχο την επίτευξη των Ευρωπαϊκών στόχων Βιωσιμότητας.

Επίπεδο: Διακυβέρνηση, Πολυεπίπεδο, Επένδυση, Εξοικονόμηση, Έργο, για τον άριστο τρόπο διαχείρισης των μέτρων εξοικονόμησης ενέργειας στην διακυβέρνηση έργων.

Αιτίες: Πολυεπίπεδο εργαλείο εργασιών που εστιάζει στην ενίσχυση των στόχων διακυβέρνησης και διασφάλιση της αποτελεσματικότητας των επενδύσεων, των ΣΔΑΕΚ, και ΣΔΑΕΚ.

Υποδομή και υλοποίηση διακίνησης μεταξύ Δημόσιου, Επένδυσης, Εξοικονόμησης, Εργασιών, Διακίνησης, Επένδυσης, Εξοικονόμησης, Έργων.

Κατερίνα Σφακιανaki CRES (Guest)

Διαδίκτυακο Σεμινάριο 07.02.2024

Διαδίκτυακο Σεμινάριο

Recording has started
Let everyone know they're being recorded

Participants

- Evdoxia Barmpa (Guest)
- ERINI VASILAKI (External)
- Evastha Kosta (Guest)
- Evastha Kosta (External)
- georgina piligioti (Guest)
- Katerina Sfaika (Guest)
- kiki (Guest)
- Kristina Chrysant (Guest)

WEBINAR: INNOVATIVE FINANCING FOR BUILDINGS' ENERGY EFFICIENCY PROJECTS

WEDNESDAY
07 FEBRUARY 2024

TIME
13:00 - 15:00
Greek time

REGISTRATION

Funded by the European Union

ΔΙΑΔΙΚΤΥΑΚΟ ΣΕΜΙΝΑΡΙΟ: ΚΑΙΝΟΤΟΜΟΙ ΜΗΧΑΝΙΣΜΟΙ ΧΡΗΜΑΤΟΔΟΤΗΣΗΣ ΓΙΑ ΕΡΓΑ ΕΞΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΗΣΗΣ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ ΣΕ ΚΤΗΡΙΑ

ΤΕΤΑΡΤΗ
07 Φεβρουαρίου 2024

ΩΡΑ
13:00 - 15:00
ώρα Ελλάδος

ΕΓΓΡΑΦΗ

Funded by the European Union

PRODESA
Ένα έργο μεγάλης διάστασης με άμεσο αντίκτυπο σε 460.000 δημότες

Energy Efficiency Project Development for South Attica - PRODESA

Διάρκεια: 2017 -2022

Χρηματοδότηση: 'Project Development Assistance' του H2020 Horizon 2020 Energy Efficiency

Εταίροι: 13 εταιρείες (Αλιμος, Αγ. Δημήτριος, BBB, AAK, Γλυφάδα, Π. Φάληρο, Μαρούσι, ΚΕΔΕ, ΕΥΔΙΤΗ, ΚΑΠΕ, ENFINITY, ECN, Κελεμένης Δικηγορική Εταιρεία)

7 Δήμοι συνεργάστηκαν:

- Ωρίμανση υποδειγματικών έργων ενεργειακής απόδοσης
- Ομαδοποίηση μικρών έργων σε μεγαλύτερα έργα κλίμακας
- Συγκοσμομό χρηματοδοτικών πηγών με έμφαση στη μόχλευση ιδιωτικής χρηματοδότησης (ΣΕΑ)

ProDeSA Energy Efficiency Project Development for South Attica

PROSPECT+

Capacity building for cities and regions - from learning to action!

Ενίσχυση ικανοτήτων Δήμων και Περιφερειών για την αξιοποίηση καινοτόμων χρηματοδοτικών εργαλείων μέσω του προγράμματος ενδυνάμωσης PROSPECT+

Στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος - TEESlab (Πρωτ. Πρωσία)

AK

ACTIVITY #8 Methodologies and tools for planning and prioritising energy saving interventions at local level (April 2024)

Type of activity:	In person event
Date & location:	19 April 2024 @Philippos Hotel, Athens
General info & needs addressed:	CRES, in collaboration with SYMPRAXIS Team and another EU-funded project re-MODULEES, organised an open event in the heart of Athens. The event aimed to address the energy upgrade of buildings in alignment with energy transition objectives. It was divided into two parts: The first part focused on familiarising citizens and stakeholders with existing tools and services that provide useful recommendations and assistance for upgrading buildings and residences. The second part centred on the ePLANET project and how the e-PLANET platform can support municipalities in achieving energy efficiency in public buildings and harmonising existing energy data. Industry experts and municipal representatives also delivered presentations during the event.
Responsible facilitators:	CRES responsible partner - 3OC contributor
Target audience:	The event gathered 21 people, comprising local, national stakeholders, industry experts, and citizens. It brought together a wide range of stakeholders, including government officials, industry experts, and concerned citizens.
Learning objectives:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the role of the e-PLANET project and how its platform can contribute to the energy building transition and decarbonisation, particularly in collaboration with municipalities and other industry experts. 2. Learn about the work and outcomes of two additional EU-funded projects, re-MODULEES and QUALdeEPC, and their contributions to energy efficiency. 3. Gain insights into EU and global legislation and recent regulations concerning energy efficiency in buildings. 4. Explore local initiatives organised by municipalities aimed at saving energy and raising awareness of climate change among young populations. 5. Hear industry perspectives on achieving energy efficiency and their recommendations for effective strategies.
Agenda:	https://www.eplaneth2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/ePLANET-REMODULEES-cluster-event-Agenda.pdf
Links to presentation:	https://www.eplaneth2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/ePLANET-9th-Press-Release-EN-Summary-of-Greek-CBA-event-EN-v1.0.pdf
Link to the recording:	https://youtu.be/MvHg8vYSr_4

ACTIVITIES #7 Innovative financing - Focus on Energy Efficiency and buildings @ONLINE

Empowering municipalities for energy planning

European public local authorities' network for driving the energy transition

764 Local Authorities
603 Signed MoU
24 Capacity Building Activities
129 ePPAs

Clustering governance
Clustering governance refers to managing and governing a cluster of entities from different structural levels, working together towards a common goal.

Vertical Governance
European Commission (DG ENER)
National level: National Authorities, Energy agencies
Regional level: Regional authorities, Energy agencies
Local level: Municipalities

Horizontal Governance
Municipalities

Capacity Building Activities
More than 24 Capacity Building Activities targeting technical staff of public authorities, addressing the needs identified on the pilot regions, and covering a wide range of thematic areas.

Digitalisation and harmonisation
The ePLANET platform provides with a set of tools to help pilot and follower regions implement energy transition measures, making local energy policies and decisions on evidence-based facts and figures.

7 Pilot regions:
Agency for Energy Efficiency and Environmental Protection (AEE) - South East Energy Agency (SEEA)
South East Regional Agency for Energy Management (SEREM)
Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia (GRF)
Regional Council of Asia (Liberal) (RCA)
Municipality of Pafos (Cyprus)
Municipality of Pafos (Cyprus)
Municipality of Pafos (Cyprus)

Ημερίδα
Καινοτόμα εργαλεία για την πρόωση της ενεργειακής αναβάθμισης κτιρίων με στόχο την ενεργειακή μετάβαση

Εγγραφή

19/04/2024, 09:30

Ξενοδοχείο Φίλιππος

SPADE CREES, NORTH AEGEAN REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT CENTRE, MODULUS, ePLANET, Funded by the European Union

SCAN ME

Εργαστήριο στις πολιτικές περιφέρειες

Pilot 2. GIRONA PROVINCE - Overview of the CBP

The capacity-building program for Girona comprised a set of nine activities, including four technical training sessions on the ePLANET platform, four content-focused webinars on energy communities, energy poverty, and innovative financing, and one Train the Trainer session on the Climate Sprint. All activities were conducted in Catalan with a few external speakers in Spanish. The CBP of this pilot actively collaborated with the PROSPECT+ project.

 Over 500 participants - pilot territory and scale-up in Catalunya

Table 3-2 below shows the list of the different activities.

Timeline: ePLANET officially launched the Capacity Building Programme in Girona in May 2023, following an informative, detailed email sent to all municipalities in the territory. The duration of the programme was around 12 months, with adjustments made to certain activities based on participant availability and the work and time plans of the municipalities.

Engagement strategy: The main objective of the capacity building activities organised from WP4 was to attract municipalities and other key stakeholders in Girona. However, two activities, namely 7-8-9, were co-organised with WP5 and involved stakeholders at the national level (Catalunya).

How?

- **Informative mailing** presenting ePLANET Capacity Building programme: This allowed municipalities in the territory to better understand the CBP structure, how to participate, as well as the themes covered and indicative **dates**.
- **For private activities:** Communication primarily consisted of mailing, with tailored invitations for each activity.
- **For public activities:** Mailing was utilised in specific instances, along with the use of online channels such as LinkedIn and websites belonging to responsible partners.
- DDGI as pilot lead, contributed to the invitation list and promoted the events at the territorial level. ICAEN, CIMNE and LIMA, on the other hand, contributed to attract participants at Catalunya level too.

Table 3-2 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Girona Province

3.1.2 Detailed reporting of the capacity building activities in Girona

ACTIVITY #1 Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1	
Type of activity:	In person workshop - Private
Date & location:	02 May 2023 @Girona
General info & needs addressed:	<p>The goal of the ePLANET platform is to provide digital support to municipalities in the planning, drafting, and monitoring of their sustainable energy transition plans at the municipal level through the SECAPS.</p> <p>In particular, the platform gave users the possibility to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor the progress and effectiveness of existing SECAPs. • Consult and contribute to a database of energy transition measures, associated investment, and avoided energy/emissions. • Access data visualisations at geographical level that can support municipalities and regions in drafting their energy transition plans. <p>Use Case 1-Digitalisation of SECAP will include several dashboards to show the mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. It will also enable a comparative visualisation of the SECAPs of different municipalities.</p>
Responsible facilitators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI -was in charge of organising the workshop (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchange messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session) • CIMNE created guidance materials for participants in English, translated support materials into Catalan, and facilitated the training.
Target audience:	18 participants from DDGI
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET platform and UC1 tool. <p>And practice working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply ePLANET UC1 tools to classify and determine the energy consumption trends of your municipality (and CO2 emissions). • Discuss and benchmark the different actions defined from the SECAPs.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of ePLANET platform and UC1 tool. • Exercises and discussion
Link to the recording:	All manuals will be uploaded at the end of the project as resources. Event not recorded for GDPR reasons.

ACTIVITY #1 Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 - 02 May 2023 @ DDGI, Girona

ACTIVITY #2 Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 - Part II

Type of activity:	In person workshop - Private
Date & location:	18 September 2023 @ Aula De Formació de Dipsalut Edifici Jaume Casademont
General info & needs addressed:	<p>The goal of the ePLANET platform is to provide digital support to municipalities in the planning, drafting, and monitoring of their sustainable energy transition plans at the municipal level through the SECAPS.</p> <p>Use Case 1-Digitalisation of SECAP will include several dashboards to show the mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. It will also enable a comparative visualisation of the SECAPS of different municipalities.</p>
Responsible facilitators:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI -organised the workshop. • CIMNE - created guidance materials for participants in English, will translate support materials into Catalan, and will facilitate the training.
Target audience:	This training included other representatives from other provinces in Catalunya. A total of 33 participants took part in the event, with 15 representatives from local municipalities in Girona and additional 18 hailing from municipalities in other provinces of Catalunya.
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET platform and UC1 tool. <p>And practice working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply ePLANET UC1 tools to classify and determine the energy consumption trends of your municipality (and CO2 emissions). <p>Discuss and benchmark the different actions defined from the SECAPS.</p>
Agenda:	<p>10:00h Introduction to ePLANET project</p> <p>10:30h Girona Province pilot developments</p> <p>11:00h Coffee break</p> <p>11:15h ePLANET platform (UC1) showcase</p> <p>12:00h Exercises & user's platform test</p> <p>13:00h Next steps to follow to help municipalities in the energy transition</p>
Links to presentation:	All manuals will be uploaded at the end of the project as resources.
Link to the recording:	Event not recorded for GDPR reasons

ACTIVITAT #1 Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 - Part II- 18 September 2023 @ Edifici Jaume Casademont

Casos d'ús Girona

- UC1 - Digitalització PAESC

67 Municipis de 16 Unitats de Paisatge

*Consum energètic del municipi [kWh/hab](2019)

Casos d'ús

- UC3 - Geo-eines per a la promoció de comunitats energètiques (REC & LEC)

Creació d'una eina de visualització georeferenciada per donar suport a la planificació de les comunitats energètiques locals (PV i biomassa com a FER) i la transició energètica del sector de l'edificació.

ACTIVITY #3 La pobresa energètica, concepte i com combatre la mitjançant una governança eficient - ePlanet

Type of activity:	Webinar - Public
Date & location:	23 January 2024 @Online
General info & needs addressed:	The promotion of tangible actions in energy transition is essential for the successful implementation of projects in renewables and energy efficiency, aligning with the EU targets. The initial tasks of the ePLANET project revealed a significant lack of technical expertise across various areas. Challenges include a notable absence of citizen engagement, a heightened risk of energy poverty due to escalating prices and global economic conditions, and substantial barriers in financing energy transition projects. The establishment of a robust governance structure emerges as a viable solution to overcome these obstacles and pave the way toward achieving the set goals.
Responsible facilitators:	The webinar was led and facilitated by researchers Marta Chàfer and Josep M ^a Granollers from ICAEN:
Target audience:	63 Local and regional authorities from Catalunya participated in this webinar
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define and articulate the concept of energy poverty, exploring various definitions, measurement methodologies, and real-world examples • Gain insights into the implementation of pilot programs dedicated to addressing energy poverty • Explore the role of support mechanisms for local entities in tackling energy poverty • Analyse successful case studies from other region • Understand the legal framework designed to protect individuals and communities from the impacts of energy poverty.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducció a la pobresa energètica: definicions, la seva mesura i exemples (Intiam) • Pla pilot de pobresa energètica (Agència de l'habitatge de Catalunya) • Suport als ens locals en l'abordatge de la pobresa energètica: Energy Poverty Advisory Hub (EPAH) i el projecte Sun4All (Ecoserveis) • 2 casos d'estudi al País Basc: Eines de rehabilitació energètica, de la visió estratègica a la implicació de la comunitat (Cíclica) • Marc legal de la protecció envers la pobresa energètica (Aliança contra la Pobresa Energètica) <p>https://icaen.gencat.cat/es/detalls/activitatagenda/20240123_webinar-pobresa-energetica-eplanet</p>
Links to presentation:	Presentation will be uploaded to the project website.
Link to the recording:	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2k1aq_AS8IE

ACTIVITY #3 La pobresa energètica, concepte i com combatre-la mitjançant una governança eficient - ePLANET - 23 January 2024 @Online

El projecte d'ePLANET
us conviden a un seminari web

LA POBRESA ENERGÈTICA
Concepte i com combatre-la mitjançant una governança eficient

23 gener 2024 @12h a 13h30 @TEAMS

Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Energia, Diputació de Girona, CIMNE, LIMA, ePLANET, Funded by the European Union

La base de dades d'indicadors nacional

Inability to keep home adequately warm

Map of Europe showing energy poverty indicators by country.

European Commission

Caracterización del parque residencial

- Caracterización arquitectónica edificio a edificio: 11 indicadores
- Caracterización energética con intervención integral y por pasos: 13 indicadores
- Caracterización económica del coste de intervención, del ahorro económico y la vulnerabilidad energética: 9 indicadores

ACTIVITY #4 Comunitats energètiques en Polígons Industrials	
Type of activity:	Webinar - Public
Date & location:	27 February 2024 @ZOOM
General info & needs addressed:	Energy communities are a key tool for decentralising and democratising the energy sector. In our territory, the primary initiatives focus on empowering citizens and local administrations to take control of their energy needs, fostering greater community involvement and decision-making. However, industries also play a crucial role in this transition, contributing to the overall sustainability and efficiency of the energy landscape. During this webinar, we delved into the potential for shared self-consumption of renewable energies within industrial areas, examining how collective efforts can lead to more efficient and cost-effective energy use. We will discuss various actions that can promote the sustainable development of an industrial energy community, considering both economic and energy perspectives. Topics will include innovative financing mechanisms, regulatory frameworks, technological solutions, and best practices from successful case studies. Our goal is to provide a comprehensive understanding of how industries can collaborate with communities to create resilient, sustainable energy systems that benefit all stakeholders.
Responsible facilitators:	Diputació de Girona and Lima
Target audience:	More than 200 participants were registered, with 150 of them attending simultaneously. Participants represented SMEs located in industrial sites, the Catalan public administration, and other stakeholders.
Learning objectives:	Potentialities of local renewable energy production and sharing in industrial sites and between SMEs
Agenda:	<p>Block 1 - Potentials of Shared Self-Consumption of Renewable Energies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy communities in industrial areas - Jaume Castellà (EPI) • Heat networks in industrial areas of Barcelona - Alex Ivancic (AIGUASOL) • Analysis of photovoltaic capacity in the industrial areas of Bages - Josep Rosell (OICOS) • SIE-Community: digitalisation of the promotion, design, and management of energy communities - (INERGY) <p>Block 2 - Real Cases from Our Territory and Tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy community in the Rosanes industrial area - Marcela Véliz (AEPIR) • Energy communities - bio-circular business model - Sami Rtimi Sboui (Alcarràs Bioproductors) • Key PAES companies for the economic transformation and future of the territory and the energy transition <p>https://www.eplaneth2020.eu/webinar-on-industrial-energy-communities-in-catalan</p>
Links to presentation:	https://www.eplaneth2020.eu/webinar-on-industrial-energy-communities-catalan
Link to the recording:	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zcvVXyWpXhU

ACTIVITY #4 Creating local energy communities in industrial environments - 7 February 2024 @Online

27 de Febrer 2024, 12h00 CET

Webinar
Les comunitats energètiques en polígons industrials

Bloc 1: Potencials d'autoconsum compartit d'energies renovables

Bloc 2: Casos reals al nostre territori

Cal inscripció prèvia

Anàlisi - vector tèrmic

- Identificació de activitats presents a cada polígon
- Realització de mapes tèrmics de cada polígon a partir de dades de consum (electricitat) i d'energia tèrmica del polígon, seguint un mètode de consum (MCM) per activitats presents a polígon
- Calibració de resultats a partir de consums industrials totals a nivell de municipi
- Mapa de consum tèrmic
- Identificació de fonts de calor residual procedent de grans indústries o de identificacions de zones calentes
- Identificació de espais tèrmiques, tenint les realitzacions com estabertes
- Mapa de focus calorífics
- Anàlisi de les zones dels focus de calor residual amb l'entorn i una primera aproximació del balanç d'energia tèrmica
- Zona a modes d'intercanvi oportunitats

Dades PAEs Bages
Potencial de generació en cobertes

Cobertes en Polígons, per Àrea Esquadrada.

Potencial instal·lable i potència instal·lable (autoconsum, abis 2023)

Polígon	Superfície (m²)	Potencial Instal·lable (kWp)	Potència Instal·lable (kW)
Polígon 1	10.000	1.000	100
Polígon 2	20.000	2.000	200
Polígon 3	30.000	3.000	300
Polígon 4	40.000	4.000	400
Polígon 5	50.000	5.000	500
Polígon 6	60.000	6.000	600
Polígon 7	70.000	7.000	700
Polígon 8	80.000	8.000	800
Polígon 9	90.000	9.000	900
Polígon 10	100.000	10.000	1.000
Total	500.000	50.000	5.000

PLA DE VIABILITAT ECONÒMICA DE LA COMUNITAT ENERGÈTICA

Per determinar l'impacte de les quotes d'autoconsum (preu MWh) en diferents zones les despeses i l'impacte al preu per pagar les factures. Tenint en compte els costos de l'EC i el valor de l'energia.

Despeses

- Despesa Operativa
- Despesa Tècnica
- Despesa EC
- Despesa energètica
- Despesa d'instal·lació

Beneficis

0€

ACTIVITY #5 Train the trainer on Climate Sprint	
Type of activity:	In person training workshop - Private
Date & location:	19/03/2024 @Casa de Cultura (Girona)
General info & needs addressed:	The Train the Trainer Climate Sprint is a specialised session designed to equip facilitators, in this case DDGI representatives, with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively conduct Climate Sprint workshops. It is a collaborative, scientific, and creative training session aimed at raising awareness about climate change in an engaging manner. Drawing on the conclusions of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), this training explores the cause-and-effect relationships behind climate imbalance. Participants also have the opportunity to familiarise themselves with the concept of the "carbon footprint," learn how to measure it, understand orders of magnitude in CO ₂ emissions, and identify impactful actions to reduce individual emissions.
Responsible facilitators:	Led by researchers Carla Barcelo and Esti Sanvicente from Three o'clock
Target audience:	8 representatives working on Consell Comarcal from the Diputacio Girona and representatives from LIMA/CIMNE
Learning objectives:	<p>Acquire the skills and confidence to effectively facilitate the Climate Sprint workshop in the pilot territory.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaining a better understanding of climate change and its consequences in different sectors. • Clarify technical questions with scientific base (based on IPCC reports) • Learning about orders of magnitude in CO₂ emissions. • Getting familiar with Carbon Footprint and how it is measured. • Identifying impactful actions to reduce individual emissions.
Agenda:	<p>09:30 - 10:00 Trainin tips to facilitate</p> <p>10:30 - 11:30 Step 1. Building the Climate Mural 📱</p> <p>11:30 - 12:00 Break ☕</p> <p>12:00 - 13:00 Step 2. What's my footprint? 🌍, Step 3. Actions to reduce it 🧑‍🌾</p>
Links to presentation:	Materials and templates will be uploaded in the website
Link to the recording:	Not recorded

ACTIVITY #5 Train the trainer Climate Sprint - 19/03/2024 @Casa de Cultura (Girona)

ACTIVITY #6 Presentació de la plataforma ePLANET a altres stakeholders nacionals

Type of activity:	In person event (with 4 speakers online)
Date & location:	22/04/2024 Barcelona (ICAEN Premises)
General info & needs addressed:	Event organised within the framework of the European project ENTRACK (Energy efficiency projects in buildings: Support and financing tools) as part of the HORIZON EUROPE initiative, where a monitoring platform for energy efficiency implementations in buildings was developed to carry out comparative analysis of investments and savings. The event consisted of two parts, the first focused within the European context regarding the financing of energy efficiency projects, their issues, and lessons learned based on previous experiences. The second part of the session focused on the tools developed to carry out energy efficiency projects more efficiently. The platform developed in ePLANET was presented.
Responsible facilitators:	ICAEN and CIMNE researchers
Target audience:	Around 50 participants, including Public Catalan energy managers, Municipalities, ESCOs, Consulting/Engineering companies and stakeholders from the Public Administration
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain insights into financing energy efficiency and clean transition, and learn lessons from the EN-TRACK project. • Explore the approach to the clean energy transition from the Government of Catalonia. • Examine practical cases demonstrating the use of tools and platforms to address energy transition challenges. • Learn about the implementation of renewable energies within flexible local markets. • Understand the four different use cases of the ePLANET Platform to identify potential new users and their main interests in utilising the platform.
Agenda:	https://icaen.gencat.cat/ca/actualitat/inscripcio-conferencia-final-del-projecte-en-track/
Links to presentation:	Energy efficiency finance - Joule Assets Europe Energy efficiency in buildings financing options - European Investment Bank DEEP De-risking energy efficiency platform - Energy Efficiency financial institutions group EN-TRACK user's perspective, findings and recommendations - Eneffect
Link to the recording:	Part 1: https://youtu.be/uNyqXA7fsKc?si=ceJpfEA0FGiQGRei Part 2: https://youtu.be/8kw0LSngH5M?si=4P0U_-BFyeyPrDf

ACTIVITY #6 Presentació de la plataforma ePLANET a altres stakeholders nacionals

ACTIVITY #7 Reforç del UC1: Actualització dinàmica de les dades dels PAESCs

Type of activity:	Webinar
Date & location:	22/04/2024 @ONLINE
General info & needs addressed:	This webinar focused on reinforcing Use Case 1 - Digitalisation of SECAP, which involved the implementation of various dashboards to display mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. Additionally, it aimed to enable comparative visualisation of SECAPs from different municipalities.
Responsible facilitators:	Jordi Cipriano from CIMNE
Target audience:	17 representatives from the Diputació de Girona, Energy Transition Offices, and Municipalities' Technicians.
Learning objectives:	<p>Participants received training to enhance their skills in managing the SIE ePLANET Platform Tool.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop proficiency in working with the ePLANET platform by: • Applying ePLANET UC1 tools to classify and determine the energy consumption trends of your municipality (and CO2 emissions). • Engaging in discussions and benchmarking the different actions defined from the SECAPs.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Update of PAESCs Data (CIMNE) • ePLANET Platform Demo (CIMNE)
Link to the recording:	GMT20240422-100559_Recording_1920x1080.mp4 Manuals will be uploaded as project resources.

ACTIVITY #6 Presentació de la plataforma ePLANET a altres stakeholders nacionals

The top screenshot displays the ePLANET interface with a world map and navigation tabs like 'Mapa', 'Comptabilitat', 'Anàlisi', 'Gestió', and 'Administració'. The middle screenshot shows a data table with columns for 'Projecte', 'Indicador', and 'Període', listing various projects and their indicators. The bottom screenshot shows a summary dashboard with a bar chart and a pie chart, along with a legend for 'Emissions de GEH del municipi (SECAP) (tCO₂/hab)'.

The large screenshot shows the ePLANET interface with a map of Catalonia. A data popup for Viladegúrfels is displayed, showing 'Emissions de GEH del municipi (SECAP) (tCO₂/hab)' as 0,52, 'Emissions de GEH del municipi (tCO₂)' as 422,2, and '% Desenvolupament' as 815 (hab) with a -13,21% change. The map is color-coded by emission levels, with a legend at the bottom indicating '+ 10%', 'Entre + 10 % i + 10 %', and '- 10%'.

ACTIVITY #8 Finançament innovador de comunitats energètiques

Type of activity:	Webinar
Date & location:	21 May 2024 @TEAMS
General info & needs addressed:	<p>Energy communities are a key tool for decentralising and democratising the energy sector. The key steps for their definition and implementation in our territory are clear and well-known, but access to appropriate financing mechanisms is often one of the main hurdles for energy communities to overcome.</p> <p>During this webinar, we will explore what alternatives to traditional financing exist in our territory and highlight possible financing strategies that can facilitate the initial phases of implementing an energy community.</p>
Responsible facilitators:	Diputació de Girona, Lima
Target audience:	We had over 90 participants, with 65 of them accessing the online webinar simultaneously, including representatives from the Catalan Public Administration, Energy Communities, and Stakeholders Providing Services to Energy Communities.
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn of alternative financing mechanisms for energy communities through specialists and real cases • Explore the concept of citizen participatory financing for energy communities • Analyse barriers and opportunities in financing community energy projects
Agenda:	<p>Block 1 - Alternatives to Traditional Financing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing models for energy efficiency measures, rehabilitation, and self-consumption (HOLTROP) • Citizen participatory financing for energy communities (eCROWD!) • Financing from ethical banking (COOP57) <p>Block 2 - Case Studies and Tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of barriers and opportunities in financing community energy projects: the ACCE project (GOIENER) • OECoop as a tool to realise Catalan energy communities (OSONA ENERGIA cooperative) • Financing for energy communities on publicly-owned solar rooftops (ENERGETICA coop) <p>https://www.eplaneth2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/ePLANET-Financament-Comunitats-Energetiques-agenda_v1.0.pdf</p>
Links to presentations:	https://www.eplaneth2020.eu/ca/webinar-on-innovative-financing/
Link to the recording:	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J82gF4Zis34

ACTIVITY #8 Finançament innovador de comunitats energètiques - 21 May 2024 @ONLINE

27 de Febrer 2024, 12h00 CET

Webinar
Les comunitats energètiques en polígons industrials

Bloc 1: Potencials d'autoconsum compartit d'energies renovables

Bloc 2: Casos reals al nostre territori

Cal inscripció prèvia

Etapas de financiación

Barreras a la energía comunitaria

- Tamaño de los proyectos
- Expectativas
- Confianza

Co-funded by the European Union

Creixement territorial d'OECoop més enllà d'Osona

- Actualment Osona Energia Cooperativa compta amb 38 cooperatives associades, però estem ja col·laborant amb més de 50 entitats locals a 20 comarques catalanes.
- Les associacions i cooperatives naixents troben en OECoop un suport que els **dona la confiança que podran tirar els seus projectes endavant**.
- Vam néixer a Osona però tenim voluntat de donar servei a les comunitats energètiques de tot el país.

EJEMPLOS DE CEFS EL FONDO DE DESARROLLO

- Investe en una cartera de **proyectos en fase de desarrollo**, cubriendo hasta un 70% de los costes
- Instituciones públicas** de cuatro provincias en Fides Injap poran el capital
- Cartera de 20 proyectos financiados - 10 millones de euros - 1000 empleos

5 DIMENSIONES

- ENTORNO
- ACTIVIDAD
- FUENTE DE FINANCIAMIENTO
- ENTORNO DE GOBIERNO
- COMERCIALIZACIÓN

Co-funded by the European Union

Impacte positiu per a empreses i comunitats

Ecrowd!

INICI PROYECTOS COOP FINANCIADA ESQUEMAS DE BLOCS DETALLE DE PROYECTOS FINANCIAR EL MÍO PROYECTO

INICI PROYECTOS 170.400€ INICI PROYECTOS 37 INICI PROYECTOS 19.200€

Ecrowd és una Plataforma de Finançament Participatiu

Modelo financiero tradicional

Els estalviadors desconnecten què fa el banc amb els seus diners.

Modelo participatiu ciutadà

Inversió directa, de persones a la seva comunitat

Traçabilitat financera

Préstec col·lectiu

Les empreses desconnecten l'origen dels fons que reben.

Les empreses o comunitat

Els inversors viuen l'aposta de la seva comunitat per la sostenibilitat

ACTIVITY #9 Estratègies i finançament innovador en mobilitat local i interprovincial dels PAESCs

Type of activity:	Webinar
Date & location:	28/05/2024 @ZOOM
General info & needs addressed:	Mobility and the associated energy consumption are among the main sources of carbon dioxide emissions that municipalities must address in the development of SECAPs. However, it is challenging to tackle strategies to mitigate emissions from a source rooted in policies and social and cultural structures that extend beyond the municipal scope. During this webinar, we learned about strategies implemented by various municipalities in Catalonia and across Spain and explore the alternative financing methods they have applied, among other aspects.
Responsible facilitators:	Diputació de Girona, Three o'clock and Lima
Target audience:	We had over 40 participants, including representatives from the Catalan Public Administration and stakeholders providing mobility services.
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify opportunities for innovative and European financing in the mobility sector • Evaluate proposals for improving state public incentives for electric mobility • Assess the effectiveness of incentives for shared electric mobility
Agenda:	<p>Block 1 - Advancing Sustainable Mobility: Strategies and Innovative Financing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities for innovative and European financing in the mobility sector (PROSPECT+) • Proposal for improving state public incentives for electric mobility (AEDIVE) <p>Block 2 - Case Studies and Tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared mobility in the Balenyà Energy Community (SOM MOBILITAT) • Incentives for electric mobility in Pra (SOM MOBILITAT) • Incentives for electric mobility in Valladolid (Ayuntamiento de Valladolid) • Application of shared mobility in public-private collaboration in Gijon (Guppy) <p>https://www.eplaneth2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/ePLANET-Financament-en-mobilitat-agenda_v1.pdf</p>
Links to presentation:	Presentations will be uploaded soon on the website.
Link to the recording:	Recordings will be uploaded soon on the website.

ACTIVITY #9 Estratègies i finançament innovador en mobilitat local i interprovincial dels PAESCs - 28 May 2024 @ONLINE

28 de Maig del 2024, 11h00

Webinar
Estratègies i finançament innovador
en mobilitat local i interprovincial
dels PAESCs

Amb la participació de:

Cal inscripció prèvia

PROSPECT+
Capacity building for cities and regions - from learning to action!
**Oportunidades de financiación
innovadora y europea en el sector
de la movilidad**

ePLANET Ayuntamiento de Valladolid
IcleVa

El servei: Vehicle elèctric compartit (Carsharing)

- Selecciona el vehicle desitjat i premes el botó "Logot ara"
- Selecciona la franja horària desitjada i premes "Confirma"
- Premsa "Tall de reserva" per poder obrir el vehicle
- Premsa "Obre" per obrir el vehicle i començar a conduir

Som Mobilitat

El treball en xarxa
El projecte de Som Mobilitat es basa en crear ecosistemes de serveis de mobilitat elèctrica compartida.

Aparcaments de barri - Comunitats de mobilitat
Amb la col·laboració de persones soles, quarts, i entitats que ven sumant al projecte aparcaments de proximitat, esdevé crear la primera xarxa de carsharing elèctric del sud d'Europa (base dator)

Sumem en un mateix projecte diferents mobilitats

- Ciudadania
- Organitzacions i empreses
- Administració pública

Esquemas e instrumentos de financiación

Instrumentos UE		Instrumentos de instituciones financieras	
Programas de financiación directa	Fondos estructurales	Instrumentos BEI	Esquemas e instrumentos de financiación innovadores
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> COSSME HORIZON EUROPE LIFE INTERREG Connecting Europe Facility program (CEF) ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European social fund (ESF) European Regional Development fund (ERDF) Cohesion fund (CF) ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ELENA (European Local Energy Assistance) JESSICA JEREMIE JASMINE JASPERS MARGUERITE ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bonos verdes Contrato de rendimiento energético (EPC) PPP Crowd-funding Préstamos blandos Fondos rotatorios Financiación de facturas

Si no es mediante subvenciones, ¿entonces cómo?

HAY MUCHAS OPCIONES, Y A MENUDO MÁS FLEXIBLES Y RÁPIDAS QUE LAS SUBVENCIONES. NOSOTROS NOS CENTRAREMOS EN:

- Financiación Ciudadana citizens finance (crowdfunding and cooperativas)
- Contratos de rendimiento energético Energy Performance Contracting (EPC)
- Contratación interna Internal Contracting (intraacting)
- Bonos Verdes Green Bonds
- Fondos de Garantía Guarantee Funds
- Préstamos Blandos Soft Loans
- Fondo Rotatorio Revolving Funds
- Financiación por Terceros Third Party Financing
- + BEI Instrumento ELENA EIB ELENA facility

Pilot 3. ZLÍN REGION - Overview of the CBP

Overview of activities

The capacity-building program for Zlín Region comprises a set of 8 activities, two in collaboration with WP5, including technical trainings and content-focused sessions on governance, innovative financing for solar energy communities, and buildings. Additionally, two extra internal training sessions were organised to train EAZK to provide technical sessions in the pilot territory. All activities were conducted in Czech and in person. In various cases, sessions were organised within the framework of larger events to increase participation. Events were not recorded for GDPR reasons.

Table 3-3 below shows the list of the different activities.

 340 participants to date - territory and scale up

Table 3-3 below shows the list of the different activities and the dates.

Timeline: ePLANET will launch the Capacity Building Programme in Zlín Region in May/June 2023. The duration of a cycle is flexible, ranging from **8 to 12 months**, depending on the availability of participants and the work plan and time plan of the municipalities. Final dates were agreed during the M18 meeting in Paris (France).

Specificity of the CBP in Zlín Region: Unlike the other two pilots, in the case of the Zlín region, there is no other technical partner in the consortium that can support EAZK to facilitate capacity building activities in Czech. Therefore, the workload will be more important for this pilot partner.

Engagement strategy: To attract municipalities and other key stakeholders in Zlín Region to participate in ePLANET capacity building activities.

How:

- **Informative webinar: general introduction to the ePLANET project and tools and the Capacity Building Programme.** One informative webinar will be organised at the beginning of the CBP, and guidance materials will be available for participants through the ePLANET website, so that they better understand the CBP structure, how to participate, as well as the themes covered and indicative dates.
- **For private activities** - EAZK will engage through phone calls and mailing.
- **For public activities** - website channels and mailing.

Table 3-3 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Zlín Region

3.1.3 Detailed reporting of the capacity building activities in Zlín region

ACTIVITY # 1 Launch of the Capacity Building Programme in Zlín Region	
Type of activity:	In person sessions
Date & location:	09 - 11/10/2023 Zlín Region governor's Day @ Valašské Klobouky
General info & needs addressed:	<p>In the first session, the ePLANET project was presented, along with an invitation to a series of seminars and webinars organised by EAZK in 2023-2024 as part of the project. EAZK also seized the opportunity to announce the launch of the ePLANET Capacity Building Programme in the Zlín Region during the governor's day organised by the Zlín Region. Miroslava Knotková, director of EAZK, introduced the ePLANET project and upcoming capacity-building initiatives to the audience. The agenda of the event encompassed regional issues related to transport, environment, tourism, strategic development, education, and culture.</p> <p>In the second session, EAZK introduced the launch of the ePLANET Capacity Building Programme in the Zlín Region at a conference organised by the e-stat company titled "Effective Energetics." Jan Vidomus, an energy specialist at EAZK, presented the ePLANET project and upcoming capacity-building activities to the audience. The conference featured various stakeholders from the Zlín Region and the Czech Republic who delivered presentations on energy transition in the Czech Republic.</p>
Responsible facilitators:	Miroslava Knotková (director) and Jan Vidomus (project manager) - Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
Target audience:	<p>A. 44: Mayors and other representatives of municipalities of the Zlín Region, Energy facilities of the Zlín Region and Energy Consultancy Companies</p> <p>B. 40 Members of the Council of the Zlín Region, Representatives of the Regional Office of the Zlín Region, Mayors and other representatives of municipalities of the Zlín Region, Energy facilities of the Zlín Region</p>
Learning objectives:	Introduction of the overall idea of the ePLANET project and invitation to the series of seminars and webinars organised by EAZK in 2023-2024 as part of the ePLANET project
Agenda:	ePLANET Capacity Building Programme in the Zlín Region was introduced to the audience
Links to presentation:	<p>Konference efektivní energetiky - Zlín (youtube.com)</p> <p>Zlín Region - Files - Nextcloud (beegroup-cimne.com)</p>

ACTIVITIES TO KICK OFF THE CAPACITY BUILDING PROGRAMME IN ZLIN REGION - 09/10/2023 @Zlín

ACTIVITY #2 Governance of the Energy Transition	
Type of activity:	In person workshop
Date & location:	09 November 2023 @ Brno
General info & needs addressed:	The director of Energy Agency of the Zlín Region, Miroslava Knotková, took part in the first meeting of newly established “Interregional energy platform of regions of the Czech Republic” which aims to define and cooperate in the most urgent issues in energy common for all regions in the Czech Republic. Energy agency of the Zlín Region took an active part at this meeting and introduced a clustering governance concept developed by ePLANET project. This concept identifies opportunities for regions to play more active role in ongoing energy transition. As an example, how to cope with challenges on regional issues related to governance facilitation and data management, the newly developed ePLANET platform, particularly UC2 - performance of public building stock, was introduced to the audience.
Responsible facilitators:	Miroslava Knotková (director) from the Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
Target audience:	29 participants, including stakeholders from all 14 NUTS Regions of the Czech Republic represented by regional authorities or regional energy agencies. 5 other energy facilities from various parts of the Czech Republic
Learning objectives:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the goals and framework of the newly established Interregional Energy Platform of Regions of the Czech Republic. 2. Learn about the clustering governance concept developed by the ePLANET project and its application in regional energy transition. 3. Explore the functionality and benefits of the ePLANET platform, especially UC2 - performance of public building stock. 4. Share best practices and experiences related to governance facilitation and data management in energy transition. 5. Foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among regional authorities and energy agencies in the Czech Republic.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the Interregional Energy Platform • Clustering Governance Concept • Presentation of the ePLANET Platform • Case Studies and Best Practices

ACTIVITY#2 - Governance of the Energy Transition during the “Interregional energy platform of regions of the Czech Republic” - 09/11/2023

ACTIVITY #3 Training-presentation on the ePLANET platform Focus on UC2

Type of activity:	Workshop - Energy efficiency in public buildings, project financing from current programs and their monitoring through the ePLANET platform
Date & location:	20.11.2023 @Zlín
General info & needs addressed:	<p>The meeting was organised as part of the ePLANET events to accelerate the energy transition in the Zlín Region. Mayors of the Zlín Region were invited to participate and were introduced to the ePLANET platform, particularly focusing on the performance of building stock (UC2).</p> <p>To make the event more attractive and relevant, other topics related to the energy transition were included, such as increasing the energy self-sufficiency of the Zlín Region, the development of energy communities, and national financial tools supporting various types of energy efficiency (EE) projects at the local level.</p>
Responsible partner/facilitators:	Miroslava Knotková (director) and Jan Vidomus (project manager) from Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
Target audience:	56 participants, including mayors and other representatives of municipalities of the Zlín Region, Energy facilities of the Zlín Region and Energy Consultancy Companies.
Learning objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the functionalities and benefits of the ePLANET platform, particularly UC2, focusing on the performance of public building stock. • Gain knowledge of various national financing tools supporting EE projects at the local level, including new calls from the OP Environment Modernization Fund and the New Green Savings Scheme. • Learn about best practices in energy efficiency and project financing. • Explore the development and benefits of local energy communities. • Discover innovative financing options for buildings and public lighting projects.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Showcase of ePLANET platform ○ Best practices ○ Local energy community ○ Innovative financing - Focus on buildings and public lighting ○ Interactive session

ACTIVITIT #3- Training-presentation on the ePLANET platform on UC1/UC2 - 20/11/23 @Zlín

ACTIVITY #4 Training-presentation on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC2

Type of activity:	Workshop
Date & location:	11 december @Zlín
General info & needs addressed:	The workshop focused on energy efficiency in public buildings, project financing from current programs, and their monitoring through the ePLANET platform. It was organised as part of the ePLANET events to accelerate the energy transition in the Zlín Region. Mayors of the Zlín Region were invited to participate and were introduced to the ePLANET platform, particularly the part related to the performance of building stock. To enhance the event's attractiveness, additional topics related to the energy transition were included, such as increasing the energy self-sufficiency of the Zlín Region, experiences with energy management in the city of Prostějov from the Olomouc Region, the development of energy communities, and national financial tools supporting various types of EE projects at the local level.
Responsible partner/facilitators:	Miroslava Knotková (director) and Jan Vidomus (project manager) from Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
Target audience:	38 participants, including: Mayors and other representatives of municipalities of the Zlín Region, Energy facilities of the Zlín Region and Energy Consultancy Companies.
Learning objectives:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Showcase the ePLANET platform, particularly UC2, focusing on the performance of public building stock. 2. Share best practices in energy efficiency and project financing. 3. Explore the development and benefits of local energy communities. 4. Understand innovative financing options for buildings and public lighting. 5. Highlight the importance of mutual cooperation and regular data updates for energy consumption on the ePLANET platform. 6. Provide an update on the current situation in Czech legislation related to energy communities. 7. Introduce national financing tools supporting EE projects at the local level, particularly new calls from the OP Environment Modernization Fund and the New Green Savings scheme.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase of ePLANET Platform • Importance of Data Cooperation • Current Legislative Update • Best Practices • Local Energy Community Development and Innovative Financing

ACTIVITY#4 - Training-presentation on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1/UC2 - 11 November 2023 @Zlín

ACTIVITY #5 Workshop on project development and financing resources (National context)

Type of activity:	In person workshop
Date & location:	11 January 2024 @Hradec Králové, Czech Republic
General info & needs addressed:	<p>The workshop was part of the Interregional Energy Platform of the Czech Republic 1/2024. The agenda focused on exchanging experiences in constructing intelligent buildings, installing renewable energy sources (RES), developing regional strategies, installing charging stations, participating in regional investment preparations, and applying energy-efficient practices.</p> <p>The Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK) took an active part in this meeting, introducing the Zlín Region's approach to project development and financing with reference to the ePLANET platform as a new integral part of the decision-making process. Available financing sources were highlighted, with a special focus on national programs such as OP Environment, NP Environment, and the Modernisation Fund. Alternative financing methods, such as Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) and citizen cooperatives, were also mentioned, though the current emphasis is on utilising available national sources for financing energy efficiency (EE) and RES projects.</p>
Responsible partner/facilitators:	Jan Vidomus (Project Manager) from the Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
Target audience:	17 participants, including representatives from 9 NUTS Regions of the Czech Republic, regional authorities, and regional energy agencies.
Learning objectives and agenda:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the process of project development and the various financing resources available. 2. Gain knowledge of best practices in intelligent building construction and RES installation. 3. Learn about the strategic approaches of different regions regarding energy transition. 4. Explore the role of the ePLANET platform in the decision-making process for energy projects. 5. Identify national programs and alternative financing methods for EE and RES projects.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Development and Financing Resources • Best Practices in Intelligent Building Construction • Installation of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) • Regional Strategies for Energy Transition • Installation of Charging Stations • Participation in Regional Investment Preparations

ACTIVITY#5 - Training-presentation on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1/UC2 - 11 January 2024 @Hradec Králové

ACTIVITY #6 Training-presentation on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC4

Type of activity:	In person workshop
Date & location:	15 May 2024 @ Zlín
General info & needs addressed:	<p>Workshop on RES Development in the Zlín Region</p> <p>This session included a training-presentation on the ePLANET platform with a focus on UC4. The meeting was partly hybrid, with the presentation by the State Environmental Fund given online from Prague.</p> <p>Mayors and representatives of municipalities within the Zlín Region were invited to participate and introduced to the ePLANET platform, specifically, the part related to the PV potential analysis. To enhance the event's attractiveness, other topics related to the energy transition were included, such as fire safety requirements for PV installations, best practices using Local Energy Concepts, current financing support from the State Environmental Fund, and experiences with the new energy law and energy sharing in apartment buildings.</p>
Responsible partner/facilitators:	Miroslava Knotková (director) and Jan Vidomus (project manager) from Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
Target audience:	36 participants including Mayors and other representatives of municipalities of the Zlín Region, Energy facilities of the Zlín Region, Energy Consultancy Companies, State Environmental Fund
Learning objectives:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the functionality of the ePLANET platform, particularly UC4 - PV potential analysis. 2. Learn the fire safety requirements for PV installations. 3. Review good practice examples using the Local Energy Concept and the calculation tool for the potential of community energy. 4. Gain knowledge about the current financing support available from the State Environmental Fund. 5. Understand the new energy law and experiences with energy sharing in apartment buildings.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase of ePLANET Platform • Explanation of the requirements each PV plant must meet from the perspective of fire safety. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Presentation of good practice examples using the Local Energy Concept. □ Demonstration of a calculation tool for assessing the potential of community energy. • Introduction to current financing support options for mayors and representatives of municipalities in the Zlín Region. • Presentation by a representative of iKomunita company, discussing the new energy law and experiences with energy sharing in apartment buildings.

ACTIVITY#6 - RES development in our Region (Training-presentation on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC4)

„Lídr v podpoře renovace budov veřejného sektoru s cílem snížení jejich energetické náročnosti...“

Aktuální možnosti podpory...

Operační program Životní prostředí

- komplexní renovace budov, včetně instalace OZE (elektrina i teplo), s min. cílem **30% úspory energie**
- celá ČR mimo budov v Praze
- příjem žádostí do června 2024
- podpora cca 50% (jednotková dotace)
- alokace 5 mld.

STÁTNÍ FOND ŽIVOTNÍHO PROSTŘEDÍ ČESKÉ REPUBLIKY

Účastníci

- TP Tomáš Pavučka
- JK Jan Kratochvíl (Externí)
- KP Křivan Pavel (Externí)
- LM Libor Mareš (Externí)
- LS Lubomír Šulc (Externí)
- R Růžička Petr (Externí)
- PE Petr Ledeš (Externí)
- PH Petr Bubeník (Externí)
- P Právník
- David Jemelka (O)
- JAK Jakub Václavík (Základní účastník)
- AL Alena Luptáková (Externí) (Základní účastník)
- PK Petr Křivan (Externí) (Základní účastník)
- BA Barbora Janáková (Externí) (Základní účastník)
- RM Roman Kalný (Externí) (Základní účastník)
- SP Štěpán Štěpánek (Externí) (Základní účastník)

ACTIVITY #7 Innovative financing (Part I) -Focus on solar and energy communities

Type of activity:	In person workshop
Date & location:	21 May 2024 @ Zlín
General info & needs addressed:	<p>The workshop was organised as part of the ePLANETS events aimed at accelerating the energy transition in the Zlín Region. This session, titled "Innovative Financing (Part I) - Focus on Solar and Energy Communities," was partly hybrid, with a presentation by the State Environmental Fund given online from Prague.</p> <p>Mayors and representatives of municipalities within the Zlín Region were invited to participate and were introduced to the ePLANET platform, focusing on the financing of energy efficiency projects and establishing energy communities. Other topics related to the energy transition were also discussed, including fire safety requirements for PV installations and best practices for using Local Energy Concepts.</p>
Responsible partner/facilitators:	Miroslava Knotková (director) and Jan Vidomus (project manager) from Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
Target audience:	55 participants, including: Mayors and other representatives of municipalities of the Zlín Region, Energy facilities of the Zlín Region, Energy Consultancy Companies and State Environmental Fund.
Learning objectives:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand the functionality and benefits of the ePLANET platform. 2. Learn about the PV potential analysis module (UC4) on the ePLANET platform. 3. Explore innovative financing options, focusing on solar energy and energy communities. 4. Gain knowledge about fire safety requirements for PV installations. 5. Review best practices for using Local Energy Concepts. 6. Understand the current and future energy legislation for public buildings. 7. Learn about the economic benefits and technical conditions of energy accumulation under the new energy law (LEX OZE III).
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase of ePLANET Platform - UC4 • Fire Safety Requirements for PV Installations • Financing Support from the State Environmental Fund • Presentation by State Energy Inspection on current and future energy legislation for the construction and modernisation of public buildings. • How to read and interpret Energy Certificates. • Interactive Session

ACTIVITY #7 Innovative financing (Part I) -Focus on solar and energy communities - 21 May 2024 @Zlín

ACTIVITY #8 Innovative financing (Part II) - Focus on buildings

Type of activity:	In person workshop
Date & location:	23 May @ Zlín
General info & needs addressed:	<p>The workshop, organised by the Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK), aimed to introduce enterprises to the main conclusions from the ePLANET project and discuss energy measures in buildings and their financing. This event was part of the planned ePLANETS events designed to accelerate the energy transition in the Zlín Region.</p> <p>The seminar's objective was to familiarise participants with support opportunities for energy-saving measures in enterprises, particularly from the Modernization Fund and the Operational Program (OP) Technology and Applications for Competitiveness. Additionally, examples of possible cooperation on community sharing of electricity were presented.</p>
Responsible facilitators:	Miroslava Knotková (director) and Jan Vidomus (project manager) from Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
Target audience:	24 participants, including representatives from enterprises, energy companies, and consultancy companies from the Zlín Region and bordering regions.
Learning objectives:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Showcase the functionalities and benefits of the ePLANET platform. 2. Introduce the UC4 module on PV potential analysis. 3. Discuss innovative financing options, focusing on energy measures in public buildings.
Agenda:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation highlighting the features and benefits of the ePLANET platform - Demonstration of the UC4 module focusing on PV potential analysis. • Discussion on innovative financing options for energy-saving measures in public buildings. • Presentation on support opportunities from the Modernization Fund and OP Technology and Applications for Competitiveness. • Discussion on the concept of community sharing of electricity. • Examples of successful collaborations and potential benefits for enterprises • Interactive Session

ACTIVITY# -

4 Key takeaways and next steps

In Task 4.3, we co-designed and implemented a tailor-made capacity building strategy and plan across each pilot territory. A total of 24 capacity building activities were conducted, with eight activities dedicated to each pilot territory. These activities proved invaluable, serving as a crucial avenue for disseminating knowledge and fostering collaborative action towards energy transition goals.

A notable aspect of these capacity building activities was their detachment from municipal politics, providing participants with unbiased access to essential training and information. This freedom from political constraints enabled a more open and constructive dialogue, facilitating effective learning and collaboration.

Among the key takeaways from these activities, several notable insights emerged:

1. **ePLANET Platform:** The ePLANET platform was recognised as an excellent model for facilitating regional energy planning and enhancing self-sufficiency. Discussions with technical municipal staff helped additional adjustments to facilitate an integrated digitalised process for the energy transition of municipalities. Such adjustments would not only streamline the use of the ePLANET platform but also enhance the overall efficiency of municipal energy transition efforts.
2. **Cooperation and Data Updating:** Mutual cooperation among municipalities and regular updating of energy consumption data on the ePLANET platform were emphasised as crucial for effective energy transition efforts.
3. **Organisational Structure:** Participants stressed the importance of a dedicated municipal officer-governance structure to manage sustainable energy transition plans and projects, alongside hiring highly qualified personnel for effective implementation and long-term sustainability. Results of ePLANET were, therefore very valuable.
4. **Urgency in Action:** Swift action through structured financing and awareness-raising efforts was highlighted as essential.
5. **Public Sector Potential:** The public sector was acknowledged for its high potential to drive additional actions towards energy transition.
6. **Knowledge Transfer:** Successful knowledge transfer to other municipalities and public bodies interested in creating Energy Communities (citizen and industrial ones) was noted, with notable interest from municipalities in the three pilot regions. Also, in relation to innovative financing in both the energy and transport sector.
7. **Role of Local Authorities:** The crucial role of local authorities in implementing bottom-up approaches to alleviate energy poverty was recognised.
8. **Just Energy Transition:** Advocacy for actions to mitigate energy poverty as a crucial component of achieving a just Energy Transition that leaves no one behind was emphasised.

The execution of training activities across various pilot sites was pivotal for maximising their potential for future scalability and replicability. Moving forward, in alignment with Task 4.4 and drawing from the insights gained and key findings, we will pinpoint training materials tailored to diverse target audiences, including policymakers, technical officers, new ePLANET facilitators, and territorial coordinators. These materials will be consolidated within the ePLANET repository in collaboration with WP5 and WP7. The submission of D4.4 is planned for M36.

